

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF TEACHING ENGLISH FROM EARLY CHILDHOOD

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Abstract: *Through this article, we are going to explore important peculiarities of teaching English from early age. Moreover, significance of learning languages in developing child's brain and communication skills were discussed.*

Key Words: *young learners, kindergarten, learning languages, opportunity, word games, capacity, education, creativeactivities.*

Let us this article begin by discussing why English for children matters in the early years of their education. Over one billion people speak English around the world. In addition, unusually, more people speak English as a second language than as their mother tongue. English is the language of international business, diplomacy, education, finance and even aviation. In other words, it is an essential life skill for the 21st century. However, these are not the only benefits of learning English for kids. Learning languages as a child is also very good for their brain. English as an international language is used and taught in many countries over the world. Teaching and learning English have become a demanding task of our education system. A lot of attention is paid by our government to teaching English from early age, from kindergarten. If we speak about young learners, they have a limited attention than adults; young learners are easily motivated in learning language if teacher gives them the interesting activities (Ur, 1999). The language learning approaches use to teach young learners best through discovery, experimentation (Tavil&Isigag, 2009). Children want to play, have fun, and make friends so they are going to learn from whatever around them relatively quickly. Therefore, the learning and teaching processes should be well matched with the nature of children learning. There are different engaging, play-based, and creative activities to teach English in classroom such as songs, games and stories. They are enjoyable and motivating activities so a desire to continue learning is created and learners want to come back (Tavil&Soylemez, 2008). Moreover, they can be used in the classroom to keep English learning interesting and to support textbook learning since students seem to be fond of working outside of the textbook. All these activities are considered as the right techniques used to teach English to young learners.

Young children have an amazing capacity to absorb a vast amount of new information in their brains. This means that when it comes to languages and skills, they are able to pick them up more easily than adults are. Research from Lund University in Sweden has proven that learning a second language can even make brains grow larger!

Children who learn English also have the opportunity to practice their communication skills. Through playing word games, speaking in front of a group and practicing conversational routines, they gain social skills and confidence.

Like any other educational institute, teachers are the backbone of the entire preschool system. These teachers, young and experienced, are entitled to the task of educating children on their eating habits, reading skills, toilet habits, and developing their cognitive skills. If it possible English is recommended to be taught in kindergarten. There is variety of ways, methods of teaching foreign languages, particularly English. Nevertheless, teacher should adopt these methods for his students according to their age, interests and individual abilities.

In the 21st century, the significance of communication skills and the English language in particular, has become paramount. In short, communication comes prior to all other skills required to move up the ladder and achieve goals, irrespective of the field chosen. After all, effective and strong communication skills are the key to accomplish every other milestone in your child's career. It is evident just how important English as a language is in today's world. Many global businesses conduct meetings in the English language, in several universities English is the medium of instruction for teaching many courses and, tourists and travelers around the world use English as a common language. English is a language of information technologies, moreover most of the masterpieces of art, literature, science are written in English. Consequently, learning English should be taught as earlier as possible.

Teaching your kids English will help boost memory, problem-solving skills, critical thinking skills, and develop an ability to multitask. In addition, children good in other languages display a sign of enhanced creativity and mental flexibility. Feeding their brains, right is equally important and it comes with the skill of learning a second language.

Strong communication skills help a child in many ways. It enhances their ability to connect with people at a global level in later life, develops confidence, preparing kids to make them understand how to present themselves before the world. It enables them to communicate well their stance in different situations.

The chances of excelling in academics is yet another benefit, as there are cognitive benefits of learning a language, it will have a direct impact on your child's academic achievement. It also helps in nurturing their curiosity, tolerance, cultural sensitivity, and most importantly, empathy. It opens a world of opportunities for them later on.

Poetically speaking, preschool instructing is no less than an art form. Envision yourself directing a bunch of young children who are wandering out of their

consolation zone for the primary time, and instructing them the essential aptitudes of life. Not each child is similar, not each child requires the same amount of care; to be able to fulfill the wants of a child, and to empower them to start becoming independent in their activities is what preschool educating is all around. Hence, a preschool educator is no less than an artist commanding a bunch of young ones.

Why we are talking about this? A very simple answer for this is our ignorance of the importance of preschool education. In a country where pre-schooling has only recently become popular and termed important for many obvious reasons, there still exists uncertainty and lack of surety as to how a preschool functions and what it aims to achieve. This paper, therefore, aims to remove that uncertainty by explaining in simple terms how preschool functions, and the methods it adopts to teach children.

Begin Early

If kids are introduced to the English language much earlier, it can help them stay ahead of their peers. Learning a language takes years. However, it is not only about merely learning the language but also keep refining and mastering the skills that one has acquired.

There's no minimum age to start learning a language, the sources of learning can be many and are not only restricted to books and academics. To make them excel in learning a language, you would need to start early. Language acquisition in kids is an incredible factor so there's no such defined age when it comes to teaching your child an extra language as kids are born with the capability to reproduce words.

The time a learner would get to devote to learning a language has a direct and positive correlation to cognitive development. It also allows them to grow alongside the second language and culture, developing a deeper connection, as they grow older. In addition, when kids learn a language at a very young age, they have a much better chance of not having a foreign accent when speaking another language, rather they sound natural.

The fact that the face of 21st century Uzbekistan has changed drastically due to globalization, understanding English has become the dire need of the hour, as it will help kids through their school and college years, and their professional life as well. It is never too late to learn a language. In fact, the language learning process is an ongoing process that never really ends. Learning English is going to ensure that your child becomes culturally aware, is at par with their peers and is able to carve a niche for itself in today's competitive world.

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